

The Transcription Challenge Framework (TCF)

Laura Morreale, Independent Scholar
lmorreale3@gmail.com

Document 1: History, Basics, Rationale

When academic workers abandoned their usual activities in March 2020 as a response to the COVID-19 threat, many wondered how to continue their research efforts in the new virtual-only environment. In restricting access to some research materials, pandemic conditions tasked scholars to think creatively about the rich resources on offer in the digital format, and to find ways to come together in non-traditional spaces to share ideas and expertise. A series of two transcription competitions, called [La Sfera Challenge](#) and [La Sfera Challenge II](#), answered this call by bringing together nearly 70 medievalists over the course of Summer 2020 to collaboratively transcribe eight copies of Goro Dati's fifteenth-century geographic textbook, *La Sfera*. The [Challenge's two iterations](#) took place between three teams from May 22-June 5, 2020, and five teams from July 17-31.

Responses to the two combined Challenges were overwhelmingly positive, with participants calling for additional opportunities to collaborate with teammates and to explore, in more detail, the materials they came to know so well during each two-week period. The success of these first events and the interest they generated in the wider scholarly community encouraged project organizers Benjamin Albritton and Laura Morreale to establish the *Transcription Challenge Framework* (TCF), a set of concepts and tools to facilitate ongoing transcription Challenges and support the research outcomes and scholarly communities created during these events. The TCF provides guidelines for Challenge organizers, houses the data created during the transcription events, and encourages publication of new research on any aspect of the texts transcribed during a TCF-sponsored Challenge. The TCF is a scholar-run, community-based initiative, supported by the IIF Consortium and FromThePage.

Basic Questions

What is a Transcription Challenge?

A transcription Challenge is a two-week event in which multiple teams of 10 transcriber-scholars compete to collaboratively transcribe multiple copies of one text, transferring information from digitized manuscript images to machine-readable versions of that same material using a digital platform called FromThePage. Once the competitive phase of the Challenge is complete, each team's submission is judged by a panel of experts based on how accurately, quickly, and collaboratively the transcription

was made. Awards in the competition are nominal, but serve as a means to evaluate submissions and highlight successful or innovative methodologies and discoveries made as a Challenge unfolds.

Who is Involved? (See Document 2: [TCF Roles and Responsibilities](#))

Each Challenge is led by a **Challenge Coordinator**, supported by two editor-captains per team. The Challenge Coordinator chooses the appropriate text, decides on the number of copies to be transcribed, recruits team captains and judges, serves as the central point of information as the Challenge takes place, gathers individual team submissions for delivery to the judges panel, and promotes the Challenge within the larger scholarly community before, during, and after the Challenge's active phase. Coordinators also archive Challenge materials once the event is complete.

Each team is composed of no more than 10 members, to include 8 transcriber-reviewers led by 2 **Editor-Captains**, who may also act as transcribers. At least one of the two editor-captains should also be designated team lead.

There are no qualifications to join, but team members (**Transcriber-Reviewers**) must sign up at least one day prior to the start of the competition and be approved as a member by the team leader to participate. A panel of three **Judges** examines and adjudicates all submissions based on transcription accuracy, speed, and collaboration.

How does it work? (See Document 3: [How to Organize a Challenge](#))

Each transcription team unites around one of the IIF-compliant manuscripts designated by the Challenge Coordinator, and has 2 weeks to produce the following:

1. A key-boarded transcription of the manuscript they have been assigned,
2. A transcription statement that sets out the rules of their edition,
3. A project log that tracks team progress,
4. A webpage with at least 4 updates on team activity during the Challenge.

Each digitized manuscript page is transcribed by one team member, reviewed by a second, and approved by one of the two editors before it is considered complete. Dated transcription logs are included with each transcription submission.

The competition takes place over the course of 2 weeks, from 12:00 PM GMT on the first day until 12:00 PM GMT on the last. Teams that complete their transcriptions before the stated deadline may submit their contributions when deemed complete. The decision of the judges is final.

Why should I participate?

Although the award for the winning team is nominal, the rewards of participation are many, as past Challenge participants attest. The Challenges provide:

- hands-on experience in digital scholarly collaboration, within a restricted time-frame,
- familiarity with digitized manuscripts and tools to access and study them,
- access to a built-in, interdisciplinary scholarly community with a unifying text or work at its center,
- an opportunity to contribute meaningfully to the scholarship of a textual or illustration tradition,
- exposure to the raw materials of humanities research, in cooperation with experts in various fields,
- possibilities for further research and publication.

Many of these outcomes are visible by reading through individual team pages or scrolling through Twitter threads and [blog posts](#) from previous Challenges. See, for example, the hashtags **#LaSferaChallenge** and **#LaSferaChallenge2** for evidence of Challenge takeaways.

Rationale

What does a Transcription Challenge achieve? (Or, Creating the *Un-Edition*)

The TCF provides a sustainable working model for the scholarly community as it moves towards more collaborative and digitally-oriented research methods. Aside from the benefits it offers to individual transcribers, the data produced during each transcription event take up the foundational assumptions of textual editing as it is currently understood.

For nearly two centuries, scholarly editors have worked to collect, collate, and curate the multiple versions of individual medieval texts that often exist in widely-dispersed manuscript copies, and to produce a *critical edition*, what is understood to be a text in its most pure and distilled form. In contrast, the products that emerge from transcription Challenges unmake the prioritization of the single archetype, highlight the close attention of transcribers to the idiosyncrasies of each print or manuscript attestation (including the edition), and foreground the ground-breaking discoveries scholars often make as they engage in the transcription process.

The immediate products of a transcription Challenge -- that is, full access to multiple key-boarded transcriptions of examples from one textual tradition-- achieve the opposite of what the printed standardizing edition does. What is created, rather, is an **Un-Edition**, a mapping-out of the chaotic

variations so characteristic of medieval textual production, and a rendering of difference in machine-readable and -manipulatable format, ready for future analysis. These events promote a new way to see medieval texts and contexts and an appreciation for each copy as a cultural artefact, existing on its own terms.

Document 2: TCF Roles and Responsibilities

Designated Challenge participants are responsible for the following duties:

1. Challenge Coordinator(s)

- a. **Text.** Selects text and delivers IIF links and catalogue records to the TCF transcription portal.
- b. **Digital Presence.** Creates the central and team web pages for a Challenge.
- c. **Personnel.** Identifies team captains and judges.
- d. **Management.** Answers questions and solves problems as the event unfolds.
- e. **Final Submissions.** Coordinates handoff of submissions between teams and judges.
- f. **Publicity.** Promotes the Challenge via social media and other discipline-specific outlets before, during, and after it occurs.
- g. **Post-event Scholarship.** Facilitates second phase projects when interest arises.
- h. **Project Archiving.** Documents and archives Challenge activities and digital objects in a digital repository. May be completed in cooperation with a Project Archivist.

2. Editor-Captains (minimum 2 per team)

- a. **Team Building.** Captains recruit members for their team. Teams should ideally be in place at least 24 hours before the competition begins.
- b. **Team Organization.** At least 1 team meeting should take place to assign pages to individual team members for transcription and review, and to plan out transcription tasks and timing.
- c. **Small Reports on Team Progress and Activities.** Team captains must post a total of at least 4 updates to the team page. These posts can be authored by anyone.
- d. **Editorial sign-off.** Once all transcriptions have been prepared and reviewed in accordance with the transcription norms established by the team members and recorded in the team's transcription statement, an editor must give a final sign off. Editors and captains are often the same people, but captains may designate other team members as editors for the purpose of final sign off.
- e. **Submission Preparation.** Captains will prepare and submit the following 4 items for submission to the judges:
 - i. Link to the transcription (locked upon team completion);
 - ii. Team transcription log;
 - iii. Team transcription statement;
 - iv. A minimum of 4 (four) small reports/updates on the team webpage.

3. **Transcriber-Reviewers (maximum 10 per team, including captains)**
 - a. **Transcription and Review.** Team members should transcribe and review the materials assigned to them within the 2-week transcription period, or following the schedule established by the team captain(s).
 - b. **Communication.** Team members should use the transcription log or other team-sponsored channels (slack, twitter, etc.) to consider and resolve transcription queries as they arise.

4. **Social Media Promoters** - at least one person per team should agree to promote the Challenge via one or more social media outlets.

5. **Judges**
 - a. **Timing.** Judges should render their decisions within one month of Challenge completion.
 - b. **Announcement.** Judges may issue their decisions in whatever way they see fit, according to the criteria of accuracy, speed, and collaboration put forth in the *TCF*.

6. **Project Archivists** will work with the Challenge Coordinator to organize, catalogue, and store all project data in an open-access digital repository, and to disseminate the bibliographic details to project participants. This allows for proper credit to be assigned, and increases the findability and citability of the Challenge outcomes. Sample archived projects include the [La Sfera](#) and [Image du Monde](#) preservation packages.

Document 3: How to Organize a Challenge (for Challenge Coordinators)

The Challenge Coordinator(s) should take the following steps the when organizing a TFC Challenge:

4-6 weeks before Challenge start-date:

1. Choose a text or source. The most successful Challenge texts follow these criteria:
 - a. It exists in multiple copies;
 - b. It is relatively short (c.1200-2000 lines);
 - c. Manuscript copies are digitized and available in IIF;
 - d. **Bonus:** Organizers can demonstrate how multiple transcriptions of the text will contribute to a(ny) scholar's ongoing research agenda.
2. Identify which copies of the text are appropriate for the Challenge.
 - a. Collect the IIF manifests.
 - b. Communicate materials to the FromThePage instantiation.
3. Prepare the Challenge webpages on the TCF home page (see templates for each type listed below). Each Challenge will need:
 - a. A landing page with an introduction to the text and dates of the Challenge;
 - b. Individual team pages with links to the transcription portal, team log, and Challenge guidelines;
 - c. A page for bibliography and resources associated with the chosen text.
 - d. A page with Challenge rules and guidelines.

2-4 weeks before Challenge start-date:

4. Recruit at least one captain per team
 - a. Inform potential captains of attendant responsibilities and ask for commitment by a fixed date.
 - b. Once confirmed, provide captains access to individual team pages to post updates and participant rosters on team web pages.
 - c. Answer incoming questions and allay misgivings.
5. Coordinate participant recruitment

- a. Team captains should bear the brunt of recruitment efforts by contacting their networks, but coordinators should serve as a center point for questions, concerns, to balance teams and interests, and to ensure all teams have a positive experience.
 - b. Help with recruitment by soliciting participation via social media.
 - c. Answer incoming questions and allay misgivings.
6. Publicize the event
 - a. Use social media.
 - b. Reach out to holding repositories to inform them their items are being used in the Challenge.
 - c. Call upon institutional outlets to publicize the event in which their community members are participating.
 7. Recruit the Panel of Judges. Panels might contain a combination of the following:
 - a. A specialist in digital editing, digital scholarship, or IT;
 - b. An expert in the language in which the text is written;
 - c. A manuscript specialist or paleographer;
 - d. An expert in the history and culture of the time during which the manuscript was created.

1 week before Challenge start-date

8. Support Captains
 - a. Send a reminder email about captains' responsibilities.
 - b. Help to balance teams when needed.
 - c. Provide cover for decisions about last minute needs for team-building.
 - d. Answer incoming questions and allay misgivings.
9. Publicize!
10. Begin to gather documentation for post-challenge archiving.

During the Challenge

11. Monitor Challenge progress for any anomalies; offer help to captains if needed.
12. Promote participant contributions on social media.

13. Receive team submissions upon completion, organize, and send to judges. (see sample spreadsheet)

Once the Challenge is Over

14. Coordinate with judges to facilitate adjudication, and announce winners when complete.
15. Communicate with participants about second phase projects.
16. Archive all web pages, data, digital objects and social media materials in a digital repository ([guidelines](#) and [resources](#) available).